

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN CHILDREN

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The main tasks and goals of environmental education are to make people interested in nature and the realities that occur in it, to determine the causes of problems between people and nature, to find ways to solve them, and to have sufficient environmental knowledge. implementation of environmental protection. The tasks of ecological education are as follows:

1. development laws of society and nature; in-depth training of relations between them and preparation of a person who can think modernly;
2. to prepare a generation that knows the ecological condition of various natural areas and prepares an ecological plan for the future in the direction of socio-economic planning and production forces;
3. every person, society and various groups, categories, classes within the society, the nature in which they live, raising young people who serve to preserve its resources;
4. To explain to the members of the society the beauty of the place where they live, valleys, hills, mountains, their importance for human life and health in the development of their social, cultural, religious views and traditions.

In the implementation of the above tasks, kindergarten teachers, school and educational students, through various games and movies, connect natural and social sciences to the natural reality and ecological conditions in the place where they live. should carry out educational work and attend classes.

When such things are done, every kindergarten child, schoolchild and student will not be indifferent to the withering of a plant, the inability of a bird to fly, the burning of a hill or forest, and the useless flow of water. He feels sorry for nature, its creatures, the water he drinks, and a sense of inner desire to improve the situation arises. This is a new biological force in man. The revolution of his new intelligence will be the victory of ecological education.

On the basis of ecological education, people and members of society should behave correctly and rationally in the preservation and economical use of nature

and its resources, devote practical work to solving environmental problems, ecological education of the individual is indifferent to education and culture.

The nature of ecological education. Republic of Uzbekistan Many decisions issued by the leadership are related to nature protection expansion and improvement of work and in this field experts to meet the requirements of science and technology development preparation is provided. Our country is the solution to these problems a part of the universe in raising socio-economic development to a new level preservation of our mother nature, planning of its natural resources and use sparingly, living creatures; including clean for humans in maintaining air, water and soil, plant and animal habitats need

2. Purpose and tasks of environmental education. The main tasks and goals of ecological education are human interaction with nature and what happens in it interest in current realities, problems between man and nature to determine the causes of origin, to find solutions and measures carry out environmental protection with sufficient ecological knowledge is to increase. The tasks of ecological education are as follows:

1. development laws of society and nature; between them a person who can deeply teach relationships and think modernly preparation;
2. socio-economic planning and production forces who knows the ecological condition of different natural areas and preparing a generation that will create an ecological plan for the future;
3. each person, society and different groups, categories within society, the nature in which the classes themselves live, its service to the preservation of wealth training young people who will;
4. their social, cultural, religious views and the place where they live in the development of their traditions, the valley, the hills, the mountains beauty, their importance in human life and health conducting explanatory work

3. Directions of environmental education. One of the main directions of ecology education in our republic is the conservation of nature sustainable ecological in the economical use of various resources organization of education and general education related to this field, starting from kindergarten among employees and managers of enterprises. For this, it is necessary to carry out the following works:

1. Strengthening environmental education and training related to nature protection and correct as well as conducting pedagogical experiments and observations creation of educational textbooks in line, sufficiently highly educated it is necessary to train specialists;

2. Environmental education everywhere among different groups of the population to continuously lead, instill in students love for nature, in terms of improving their skills, preserving and saving natural resources young people should be trained as ecological economists;

3. Kindergarten, school regarding the study of reality, environmental protection from children to environmental education in senior leaders organization of short and multi-year courses that will provide them with environmental education by creating relatively durable, resilient, and tolerant skills condition;

4. Carrying out ecological education in educational institutions. Ecological ways of conducting education in kindergartens and schools. Nature, his family, kindergarten children work on preserving beauty and natural resources and starting from conducting among schoolchildren, young and growing to raise the generation to be kind to the environment, its plants, animals, water and soil, it is necessary to educate them as a soul that protects and enriches them.

1. In order to achieve these goals, kindergarten children will be trained in special "Ecological educational methodology", based on such programs as "Getting to know nature". education and environmental education about nature with the help of various games its elements should be inculcated in children's minds;

2. To instill love for nature in children special methodological manuals, recommendations, "The world around us", "Nature around us", "Natural science". in simple, simple and understandable forms based on educational and game materials should be conducted;

3. Provides environmental education to children educators and Methodists themselves have completed special courses, they must be experienced specialists;

4. Retrain educators on the basis of the "Ecological education and nature style" program organizing training courses, lectures, experience exchange seminars, improving the knowledge and levels of employees, and their working abilities need.

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